

Satisfaction with the Services Provided by the Bureau of Fire Protection

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Abstract:

In this context, this study aimed to determine the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental for the First Quarter of 2024. This information can guide improvements and help the BFP better meet community needs. Data needed for this descriptive research study was collected from 100 respondents using a self-made data-gathering instrument that has passed the stringent tests of validity and reliability. Overall, the respondents are commonly composed of younger generations, commonly female and with the micro-enterprise. Corresponding results surfaced that an outstanding level of respondents' satisfaction was shown when grouped according to three primary variables, which are age, sex, and number of employees; as such, areas of the BFP services, emergency response services, and investigative and compliance services were at a very high level. Conversely, areas of preventive services entail a need for improvement. Other than that, the result shows no significant difference in the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP when grouped according to the abovementioned variables. The study results call for all BFP personnel to actively implement and enhance the skills needed to be proactive in spreading fire safety awareness and preventive measures for a fire-safe nation.

Keywords: BFP, satisfaction level, fire and non-fire services, Bacolod City

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The BFP, established to safeguard Filipinos during calamities, is guided by legal frameworks like Republic Acts No. 6975, 9514, and 11589. Its core mission is to protect lives and property, aiming for a fire-resistant nation by 2034. Though known for firefighting and emergency response, its preventive and investigative roles are sometimes overlooked. Limited awareness of the BFP's full range of services hampers its effectiveness. Beyond firefighting, it provides essential preventive measures like fire safety lectures, permit renewals, and non-fire services such as rescue operations. It also conducts investigations and ensures safety compliance. This lack of recognition undermines the BFP's impact, emphasizing the need to evaluate personnel performance in fulfilling their core mission.

Recognizing the importance of the non-fire services provided by the BFP, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study that aims to determine the level of satisfaction of the Filipino community especially the business owners with the services provided by the BFP during the fire and non-fire responses.

Current State of Knowledge

Amidst, the ongoing modernization, the level of satisfaction of the community in terms of the services provided by the firefighters was dependent on the firefighter's personality, physical condition, behavior, and psychological characteristics along with organizational and management factors (Ardalan et al., 2021).

Parcasio et al. (2023) sought to explore the link between public awareness and satisfaction with the BFP services in San Jose City during the Fiscal Year 2023. The highlighted that the respondents were aware and satisfied with the services provided by the BFP in San Jose City. Notably, the study also showed a significant relationship between awareness and satisfaction with BFP services. The researcher recommended that young business owners and managers are encouraged to expand their expertise in running a successful business.

Aquino et al. (2017), conducted a study with the extent of the capability of the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) of Ilocos Sur in responding to emergencies. They stated in their research study that the BFP's capacity in

reacting/responding to emergencies is "Very High," which means that the firemen and some fire volunteers are prepared and ready.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study is anchored on Oliver's Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) (1980). This theory explains the level of citizens' satisfaction arises from a process in which citizens compare their perceptions of the performance of a public service against their prior expectations. This prominent theory has been the exact model approach in explaining citizen's satisfaction with public services. This powerfully supports the whole study, which involves the level of customer satisfaction with the BFP services. The services provided by the BFP must meet the client's expectations to avoid the so-called "disconfirmation". If there is a disconfirmation, it would imply that the customer or client was not satisfied with the public services of the BFP. In addition, to understand the level of satisfaction with the BFP services, this study will systematically identify the areas that need further improvement for the BFP chiefs and other officials to provide an effective recommendation that can be used to achieve the BFP's mission and vision.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental for the First Quarter of 2024. Specifically, it sought to determine; 1) the level of satisfaction of the respondents provided by the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) according to preventive, emergency response, and investigative and compliance services; 2) the level of satisfaction of the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and 3) the significant difference between the level of satisfaction with BFP services when grouped and compared according to the selected demographics.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, data gathering procedure, other instrumentations, and statistical tools. It also discusses the parameters, especially the statistical tools, the respondents' profiles, and the study's locality.

Research Design

This paper utilized the descriptive research design to determine the satisfaction level of the services provided by the BFP in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental for the First Quarter of 2024. In the study of Sircilla (2023), she noted that the descriptive research aims to provide a thorough and precise depiction of the attributes and actions of a specific population or subject. It involves observing and gathering data on a given topic without attempting to infer causal relationships.

Study Respondents

Respondents were identified using purposive sampling in which the researcher chose the respondents based on readily available subjects.

Instruments

This study employed a self-made questionnaire with 30 items on the satisfaction on the preventive services, emergency response services, and investigative and compliance services, ten items per area. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale containing the following scores with range and description: 5 – Always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – Rarely, and 1 – Almost Never.

Data Gathering and Procedure

After administering the validity and reliability, upon approval of the Chief, Fire Safety Enforcement Section, the questionnaires were administered to target respondents. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The encoded data was computer processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 and 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of satisfaction in the preventive services, emergency response services, and investigative and compliance services when grouped according to age, sex, and number of employees. Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP when they are grouped and compared according to just mentioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

By guaranteeing the confidentiality of the respondents' answers and upholding their anonymity during the whole research process, the study made a concerted effort to reduce the possibility of harm to its target respondents in accordance with Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher also requested their free and informed consent up front.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to carry out the pre-determined objectives of this study. The first objective was to determine the level of satisfaction in the preventive services, emergency response services, and investigative and compliance services.

Table 1
Level of Satisfaction in Preventive Services

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Preventive Services		
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...		
1. frequency of fire safety seminars or workshops conducted by the BFP in my community.	4.25	High Level
2. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding fire safety standards for my workplace and residence.	4.44	High Level
3. thoroughness of BFP's fire safety inspections in my community or neighborhood.	4.53	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP in raising public awareness about fire hazards.	4.60	Very High Level
5. impact of BFP's community outreach programs in promoting fire prevention measures.	4.55	Very High Level
6. efficiency of BFP's permit issuance process for businesses and events in compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.68	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's licensing and certification processes for fire safety compliance.	4.70	Very High Level
8. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding the proper use and maintenance of fire safety equipment.	4.62	Very High Level
9. responsiveness of BFP in ensuring fire safety compliance during community events or gatherings.	4.64	Very High Level
10. BFP's preventive services on the overall safety of my community.	4.64	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.57	Very High Level

Table 1 shows the level of satisfaction in preventive services, with an overall mean of 4.57, interpreted as a Very High Level. This implies that the BFP personnel still need to give more importance and utmost attention to conducting fire safety seminars or workshops within the area of responsibility. There is a need to increase the frequency of various fire safety seminars to increase fire safety knowledge in the community.

Table 2
Level of Satisfaction in Emergency Response Services

Area		
B. Emergency Response Services		
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...		
1. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.70	Very High Level
2. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.69	Very High Level
3. BFP's provision of essential medical assistance during emergencies.	4.68	Very High Level
4. coordination of BFP personnel during rescue operations in various emergencies.	4.74	Very High Level
5. level of training and expertise demonstrated by BFP personnel during emergency response situations.	4.64	Very High Level
6. BFP's communication and information dissemination during emergencies.	4.66	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's emergency response services during crises in my community.	4.67	Very High Level
8. BFP's collaboration with other emergency response units during complex incidents.	4.65	Very High Level
9. BFP provides rescue operations during non-fire emergencies, such as building collapses or natural disasters.	4.61	Very High Level
10. BFP's emergency response services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.70	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.67	Very High Level

Table 2 shows the level of satisfaction in emergency response with an overall mean of 4.67, interpreted as very high. While the BFP performs well in most areas, there's room for improvement, specifically in rescue operations during non-fire emergencies. This presents an opportunity for the BFP to focus resources and efforts on enhancing this aspect of their services even further.

Table 3
Level of Satisfaction in Investigative and Compliance Services

Area		
C. Investigative and Compliance Services		
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...		
1. thoroughness of BFP's investigations into the causes of fires in my community.	4.68	Very High Level
2. recommendations provided by BFP following investigations to prevent similar incidents in the future.	4.67	Very High Level
3. efficiency of BFP's certification process for fire safety compliance in buildings and establishments.	4.70	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding fire safety regulations for businesses and events.	4.68	Very High Level

5. level of collaboration between BFP and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards.	4.66	Very High Level
6. accessibility of BFP's compliance certification processes for individuals and organizations in my area.	4.71	Very High Level
7. BFP's responsiveness in addressing the community's fire safety concerns.	4.70	Very High Level
8. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding the importance of fire safety compliance for the overall safety of my community.	4.69	Very High Level
9. BFP's engagement with businesses and events to ensure their compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.68	Very High Level
10. BFP's investigative and compliance services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.70	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.69	Very High Level

Statistics in Table 3 reflecting the data on the level of satisfaction in Investigative and compliance services reveals that the overall mean was 4.69, interpreted as very high. The very high rating suggests that both the BFP and local communities recognize the significance of collaboration in promoting fire safety standards. This acknowledgment is crucial as it lays the groundwork for further strengthening collaborative efforts in the future. This means that the BFP personnel are responsible for investigating fire incidents for an accurate report and certification. Thus, the high rating indicates a strong performance that must be nurtured and sustained.

Level of Satisfaction with the Services Provided by the BFP When Grouped According to Demographics

The second objective was to determine the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP when grouped according to number of employees, age, and sex.

Table 4
Level of Satisfaction in Preventive Services When Grouped According to Number of Employees

Categories	Few		Many	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Preventive Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. frequency of the fire safety seminars or workshops conducted by the BFP in my community.	4.24	High Level	4.29	High Level
2. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding fire safety standards for my workplace and residence.	4.43	High Level	4.46	High Level
3. thoroughness of BFP's fire safety inspections in my community or neighborhood.	4.54	Very High Level	4.50	Very High Level
4. clarity of the information provided by BFP in raising public awareness about fire hazards.	4.55	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level
5. impact of BFP's community outreach programs in promoting fire prevention measures.	4.50	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
6. efficiency of BFP's permit issuance process for businesses and events in compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.64	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's licensing and certification processes for fire safety compliance.	4.67	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
8. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding the proper use and maintenance of fire safety equipment.	4.59	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
9. responsiveness of BFP in ensuring fire	4.61	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level

safety compliance during community events or gatherings.

10. BFP's preventive services on the overall safety of my community.	4.59	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.54	Very High Level	4.65	Very High Level

Table 4 presents the level of satisfaction with the services provided by the BFP in Preventive Services. When grouped according to the Number of Employees, with a few overall means of 4.54 and many employees with 4.65, both interpreted as a Very High Level. This indicates that both the few and many numbers of employees belong to the Micro enterprises, which are satisfied with the issuances of the BFP personnel in regards to the certificates for Fire Safety Inspection. Also, it implies that community members may not be adequately informed about fire prevention measures, emergency procedures, and proper fire safety protocols.

Table 5
Level of Satisfaction in Emergency Response Services When Grouped According to Number of Employees

Categories	Few		Many	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Emergency Response Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.66	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level
2. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.66	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
3. BFP's provision of essential medical assistance during emergencies.	4.62	Very High Level	4.88	Very High Level
4. coordination of BFP personnel during rescue operations in various emergencies.	4.68	Very High Level	4.92	Very High Level
5. level of training and expertise demonstrated by BFP personnel during emergency response situations.	4.63	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
6. BFP's communication and information dissemination during emergencies.	4.61	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's emergency response services during crises in my community.	4.63	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
8. BFP's collaboration with other emergency response units during complex incidents.	4.62	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level
9. BFP's provision of rescue operations during non-fire emergencies, such as building collapses or natural disasters.	4.58	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
10. BFP's emergency response services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.66	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.63	Very High Level	4.80	Very High Level

Table 5, the level of satisfaction in Emergency Response Services according to the number of employees, with an overall mean of 4.63 for few and 4.80 for many, are both interpreted as Very High Level. The result shows that the BFP activity in rescue operations is high. This can be supported by the study of Aquino et al. (2017), who found that the respondents are highly capable of rendering quality fire operation procedures. While the BFP performs well in most areas, there's room for improvement, specifically in rescue operations during non-fire emergencies. This presents an opportunity for the BFP to focus resources and efforts on enhancing this aspect of their services even further.

Table 6
Level of Satisfaction on the Services in Investigative and Compliance Services When Grouped According to the Number of Employees

Categories	Few		Many	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Investigative and Compliance Services				
As a business owner and community member, I				

am satisfied with the...					
1. thoroughness of BFP's investigations into the causes of fires in my community.	4.66	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
2. recommendations provided by BFP following investigations to prevent similar incidents in the future.	4.63	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level	
3. efficiency of BFP's certification process for fire safety compliance in buildings and establishments.	4.68	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
4. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding fire safety regulations for businesses and events.	4.66	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
5. level of collaboration between BFP and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards.	4.62	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level	
6. accessibility of BFP's compliance certification processes for individuals and organizations in my area.	4.70	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
7. BFP's responsiveness in addressing the community's fire safety concerns.	4.68	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
8. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding the importance of fire safety compliance for the overall safety of my community.	4.64	Very High Level	4.83	Very High Level	
9. BFP's engagement with businesses and events to ensure their compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.68	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level	
10. BFP's investigative and compliance services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.68	Very High Level	4.75	Very High Level	
Overall Mean	4.66	Very High Level	High	4.76	Very High Level High

Table 6 shows that the level of satisfaction in investigative and compliance services according to the number of employees overall mean of 4.66 for the few and 4.76 for the many, both are interpreted as Very High Level. This reflected that the BFP personnel are well-rounded in their communication skills regarding the fire prevention programs. Based on the respondents' evaluation, communication was the service quality dimension that needed improvement. It is one of the most critical dimensions the existing process cannot realize. The existing process's ability to inform applicants as to the status of their application in a convenient and timely manner was found to be very ineffective.

Table 7
Level of Satisfaction in Preventive Services When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Preventive Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. frequency of the fire safety seminars or workshops conducted by the BFP in my community.	4.25	High Level	4.24	High Level
2. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding fire safety standards for my workplace and residence.	4.49	Very High Level	4.39	High Level
3. thoroughness of BFP's fire safety inspections in my community or neighborhood.	4.55	Very High Level	4.51	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP in raising public awareness about fire hazards.	4.59	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
5. impact of BFP's community outreach programs in promoting fire prevention measures.	4.51	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
6. efficiency of BFP's permit issuance process for businesses and events in compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.71	Very High Level	4.65	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's licensing and certification processes for fire safety compliance.	4.75	Very High Level	4.65	Very High Level
8. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding the proper use and maintenance of fire safety equipment.	4.63	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
9. responsiveness of BFP in ensuring fire safety compliance during community events or	4.65	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level

gatherings.

10. BFP's preventive services on the overall safety of my community.	4.67	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.58	Very High Level	4.55	Very High Level

Table 7 reflecting the data on the level of satisfaction in preventive services according to age revealed that the younger category's overall mean is 4.58, interpreted as a Very High Level, and the older category with 4.55 interpreted as Very High Level. This reflected that both younger and older respondents were fully aware and expressive of the BFP services they had availed within their community. BFP certifications are more readily available in highly urbanized cities. It is likely an indication of improvement through the hand-in-hand collaboration of the BFP to the Local Government Units. Also, through the activeness of the BFP personnel, they join the annual Business One Stop Shop (BOSS) every January and February.

Table 8
Level of Satisfaction in Emergency Response Services When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
B. Emergency Response Services	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.76	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
2. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.76	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
3. BFP's provision of essential medical assistance during emergencies.	4.67	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
4. coordination of BFP personnel during rescue operations in various emergencies.	4.78	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
5. level of training and expertise demonstrated by BFP personnel during emergencies.	4.71	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
6. BFP's communication and information dissemination during emergencies.	4.71	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's emergency response services during crises in my community.	4.75	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
8. BFP's collaboration with other emergency response units during complex incidents.	4.76	Very High Level	4.53	Very High Level
9. BFP's provision of rescue operations during non-fire emergencies, such as building collapses or natural disasters.	4.69	Very High Level	4.53	Very High Level
10. BFP's emergency response services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.80	Very High Level	4.59	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.74	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level

Table 8 plots the level of satisfaction in the Emergency Response Services according to age, with an overall mean of 4.74 for younger and 4.61 for older; both are interpreted as Very High Levels. This suggested that the BFP's activeness to respond to any emergencies and rescue operations are readily accessible by the community. From its original mandate of just being mere fire prevention and fire suppression, the BFP is now a multi-faceted bureau whose functions other than fire prevention and fire suppression include emergency medical service and fire rescue.

Table 9
Level of Satisfaction in Investigative and Compliance Services When Grouped According to Age

Categories	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Investigative and Compliance Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. thoroughness of BFP's investigations into the causes of fires in my community.	4.67	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
2. recommendations provided by BFP following investigations to prevent similar incidents in the future.	4.69	Very High Level	4.65	Very High Level
3. efficiency of BFP's certification process for fire safety compliance in buildings and establishments.	4.67	Very High Level	4.73	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding fire safety regulations for businesses and events.	4.69	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
5. level of collaboration between BFP and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards.	4.71	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
6. accessibility of BFP's compliance certification processes for individuals and organizations in my area.	4.73	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
7. BFP's responsiveness in addressing the community's fire safety concerns.	4.73	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
8. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding the importance of fire safety compliance for the overall safety of my community.	4.75	Very High Level	4.63	Very High Level
9. BFP's engagement with businesses and events to ensure their compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.65	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
10. BFP's investigative and compliance services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.69	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.69	Very High Level	4.68	Very High Level

Table 9 data on the level of satisfaction in Investigative and Compliance Services according to age revealed that the younger overall mean is 4.69 and the older overall mean is 4.68; both are interpreted as a Very High Level. This meant that the investigative services provided by the BFP needed the utmost attention since it ensured fire compliance with safety precautionary measures. Despite being the lowest-rated aspect, the very high level indicates a generally strong foundation of collaboration between the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards. This implies that some level of partnership and communication has already been established between the two parties.

Table 10
Level of Satisfaction in Preventive Services When Grouped According to Sex

Categories	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Preventive Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. frequency of the fire safety seminars or workshops conducted by the BFP in my community.	4.08	High Level	4.36	High Level
2. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding fire safety standards for my workplace and residence.	4.31	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
3. thoroughness of BFP's fire safety inspections in my community or neighborhood.	4.36	High Level	4.64	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP in raising	4.38	High Level	4.74	Very High Level

public awareness about fire hazards.

5. impact of BFP's community outreach programs in promoting fire prevention measures.	4.33	High Level	4.69	Very High Level
6. efficiency of BFP's permit issuance process for businesses and events in compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.51	Very High Level	4.79	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's licensing and certification processes for fire safety compliance.	4.51	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
8. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding the proper use and maintenance of fire safety equipment.	4.38	High Level	4.77	Very High Level
9. responsiveness of BFP in ensuring fire safety compliance during community events or gatherings.	4.49	High Level	4.74	Very High Level
10. BFP's preventive services on the overall safety of my community.	4.41	High Level	4.79	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.38	High Level	4.69	Very High Level

Table 10 reflects the level of satisfaction in the preventive services according to sex with an overall mean of 4.38, interpreted as high for males and 4.69, interpreted as very high for females. This suggests no such distinctive difference in how male and female respondents observed and concluded regarding the BFP services they had availed within the community. Female firefighters are primarily designated in the Office, and some are assigned 24-hour duty. If there is an occurrence of fire, they will join the response team at the fire scene. Though the BFP has been adapting to the gender equality movement, the community can't deny that they feel more assured with the male firefighters than the women in uniform.

Table 11

Level of Satisfaction in Emergency Response Services When Grouped According to Sex

Categories	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Emergency Response Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.64	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
2. speed of BFP's response to fire incidents in my area.	4.64	Very High Level	4.72	Very High Level
3. BFP's provision of essential medical assistance during emergencies.	4.62	Very High Level	4.72	Very High Level
4. coordination of BFP personnel during rescue operations in various emergencies.	4.62	Very High Level	4.82	Very High Level
5. level of training and expertise demonstrated by BFP personnel during emergency response situations.	4.62	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
6. BFP's communication and information dissemination during emergencies.	4.62	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
7. accessibility of BFP's emergency response services during crises in my community.	4.64	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
8. BFP's collaboration with other emergency response units during complex incidents.	4.59	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
9. BFP's provision of rescue operations during non-fire emergencies, such as building collapses or natural disasters.	4.54	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
10. BFP's emergency response services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.59	Very High Level	4.77	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.61	Very High Level	4.71	Very High Level

Table 11 exhibits the level of satisfaction of the respondents in emergency response services based on sex, with an overall mean of 4.61 for males and 4.71 for females. Both are interpreted as a very high level (VHL). Based on the preceding results, it is noted that there is still a need for improvement, especially in the response services. With regards to the speed and effectivity of the response of the BFP personnel, it is in the Theory of Fire service Provision (2018), an empirical analysis of response time, suppression time, and service output during a fire occurrence, the outputs from the two stages are actualized into dispatch level, response time, and suppression time. There is a need to understand that in every fire call, a step-by-step procedure must be followed for a safe fire response, which applies to any emergency response. Thus, the BFP personnel are slowly moving forward for more active, immediate responses, maybe fire calls or incidents.

Table 12
Level of Satisfaction in Investigative and Compliance Services When Grouped According to Sex

Categories	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Investigative and Compliance Services				
As a business owner and community member, I am satisfied with the...				
1. thoroughness of BFP's investigations into the causes of fires in my community.	4.59	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
2. recommendations provided by BFP following investigations to prevent similar incidents in the future.	4.67	Very High Level	4.67	Very High Level
3. efficiency of BFP's certification process for fire safety compliance in buildings and establishments.	4.69	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level
4. clarity of information provided by BFP regarding fire safety regulations for businesses and events.	4.72	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
5. level of collaboration between BFP and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards.	4.67	Very High Level	4.66	Very High Level
6. accessibility of BFP's compliance certification processes for individuals and organizations in my area.	4.74	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
7. BFP's responsiveness in addressing the community's fire safety concerns.	4.72	Very High Level	4.69	Very High Level
8. effectiveness of BFP's communication regarding the importance of fire safety compliance for the overall safety of my community.	4.67	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level
9. BFP's engagement with businesses and events to ensure their compliance with fire safety regulations.	4.64	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level
10. BFP's investigative and compliance services on the safety and well-being of my community.	4.64	Very High Level	4.74	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.67	Very High Level	4.70	Very High Level

Table 12, the level of Satisfaction of the Respondents in Investigative and Compliance Services According to Sex revealed the male overall mean is 4.67, interpreted as a very high level, and female with 4.70, also interpreted as VHL. The very high rating suggests that both the BFP and local communities recognize the significance of collaboration in promoting fire safety standards. This acknowledgment is crucial as it lays the groundwork for further strengthening collaborative efforts in the future. It is duly noted that the BFP investigative services can ensure an accurate fire arson investigation report and any other certifications. The very high rating suggests that both the BFP and local communities recognize the significance of collaboration in promoting fire safety standards. This acknowledgment is crucial as it lays the groundwork for further strengthening collaborative efforts in the future.

Comparative Analysis Between the Level of Satisfaction with the BFP Services when Grouped according to Demographics

The third objective was to determine the significant difference in the level of satisfaction with the BFP services when grouped and compared according to just mentioned demographics.

Table 13
Comparative Analysis of Level of Satisfaction in Preventive Services when Grouped according to Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Number of Employees	Few	76	50.29	896.000	0.889	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	24	51.17				
Age	Younger	51	47.08	1075.000	0.194	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	49	54.06				
Sex	Male	39	45.60	998.500	0.145	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	61	53.63				

Table 13 on the difference in the level of satisfaction in preventive services when grouped and compared according to the number of employees, age, and sex with the computed p-value of 0.889, 0.914, and 0.145 which are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables, the hypothesis that there is a difference in the respondents' satisfaction level with BFP services offered in preventive services is not rejected. While the BFP performs well in most areas, there's room for improvement, specifically in rescue operations during non-fire emergencies. This presents an opportunity for the BFP to focus resources and efforts on enhancing this aspect of their services even further.

Comparative Analysis of level of Satisfaction in Emergency Response Services When Grouped and Compared According to Demographics

This area presents the comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in emergency response services when grouped and compared according to the number of employees, age, and sex with the computed p-values of 0.294, 0.938, and 0.930, which are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the respondents' satisfaction level with BFP services offered in emergency response services is not rejected.

Comparative Analysis of Level of Satisfaction in Investigative and Compliance Services When Grouped and Compared According to Demographics

This area illustrates the comparative analysis of satisfaction of the respondents in investigative and compliance services when grouped and compared according to the number of employees, age, and sex with the computed p-value of 0.202, 0.603, and 0.767 which are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the respondents' satisfaction level on BFP services offered in investigative and compliance services when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables is not rejected. The very high level indicates a generally strong foundation of collaboration between the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) and local communities in promoting and ensuring compliance with fire safety standards. This implies that some level of partnership and communication has already been established between the two parties.

Conclusion

The findings of this study are from the data gathered, analyzed, and correspondingly interpreted. With that, conclusions were drawn from the initial analysis and interpretation. A low level of satisfaction with fire preventive services typically indicates that the services provided are not meeting the expectations or needs of the individuals or communities they are meant to serve. Here are some possible implications and meanings of low satisfaction in fire preventive services: 1) inadequate services; 2) lack of awareness or education; 3) limited accessibility; 4) issue with response or effectiveness; 5) communication and engagement; 6) resource allocation; and 7) trust and confidence. In preference, a low level of satisfaction in fire preventive services is a signal that improvements or changes may be needed in how fire safety measures are implemented, communicated, and delivered to the community to better meet their needs and expectations.

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